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Features of Agricultural Production Production on Forest Fund Lands and Factors Affecting It

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ABSTRACT

In this article of the essence, features and factors influencing the improvement of the agricultural production system on forest lands are theoretically explained.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the globalization of the world economy, the need for effective and rational use of the existing high potential of the national economy and its sectors is one of the main conditions for increasing the weight and significance of our country in the world economy. One of the main natural resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the forests located on its territory. Therefore, the rational and efficient use of existing forests is one of the main tasks.

As a result of the introduction of quarantine restrictions due to global climate change and the worsening epidemiological situation on our planet, production volumes are decreasing, and meeting the population's demand for food products is becoming increasingly difficult. Because in the production of food products, 30 percent of the Earth's surface, 70 percent of agricultural crops, and 8 percent of irrigation water are used. This creates the need for saving resources in agriculture, the widespread introduction of intensive technologies and innovative developments into the industry.

In countries with developed and existing forestry, in order to organize the cultivation of agricultural products on forest fund lands, create new land areas, and protect them from fires, mechanisms of state support and incentives are being introduced, and today they are yielding high results. Large-scale scientific research in these areas is being conducted in leading world research centers and institutions not only in terms of the economic and social significance of the forest fund for agriculture, but also for the development of tourism and health resorts. These include, in particular, improving the organizational, economic,

socio-ecological foundations of agricultural production on forest fund lands and studying its environmental impact, developing integrated management models of forestry and agriculture (agroforestry), applying modern methods such as drones, GIS (geographic information systems) and information technologies in forestry, creating and placing crop types corresponding to the characteristics of forest fund lands, assessing their impact on climate change and system services.

As is known, one of the main natural resources of our republic is the forests of almost all its territories. Therefore, at the state level, special attention is paid to the directions and measures for their effective use, which is yielding positive results. However, the insufficient solution of some problems and shortcomings related to the further improvement of the forest management system, the introduction of scientific and technological achievements in order to organize agricultural production on forest fund lands and increase the efficiency of their use, strengthening and modernizing the material and technical base of the system, attracting foreign investments and increasing investment attractiveness, developing ecological tourism and increasing the efficiency of the forestry system today limits the possibilities of effective use of the existing potential in the industry.

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It should be noted that in 2017, the total land area of the forest fund was 10.5 million hectares, which is 23.4% of the total land area of our country, in 2022 it will be 12 million hectares (26.7% of the total land area of our country), that is, as a result of afforestation measures carried out over more than five years, the land area of the forest fund was increased by 1.5 million hectares. By Resolution No. PP-171 of May 31, 2023, "On the Effective Organization of the Activities of the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change," 10 hunting farms, 8 national natural parks, and 5 experimental farms were transferred to the Ministry's jurisdiction, and currently, the total land area of the forest fund is 7.1 million hectares. Of the existing forest fund lands, 3004.3 thousand hectares are forest and shrublands. The area of forests and shrubs in the republic is 7.3% of the total land area. It should be noted that on the lands of the State Forest Fund there are 63 state forestry enterprises, 7 reserves, 10 forest hunting farms, 8 national natural parks, 1 forest biosphere reserve, 5 forestry enterprises specializing in the cultivation of medicinal plants, 6 forest experimental stations, 5 production enterprises, 4 irrigation forestry enterprises, and 2 ecopytnics. 85.6% of forest fund lands are desert, 13.2% are mountainous, 0.2% are valley, and 1.0% are tugai.

2. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

It shows that there are two sharply different views on the modernization and innovative development of forestry activities. The first approach notes that forestry is a "traditional" sector with a low level of modernization and limited opportunities for innovative development, and they believe that innovative developments introduced mainly for other related industries can be used. The second point of view notes that the forestry industry has a long "traditional" history of development, and its direct features should be determined based on the main goal of production and provision of services in this sector, based not on consumer demand, but on the final result and strategic goals. The indicated approaches depend on the following factors, which differ from other industries directly affecting the modernization and innovative development of forestry:

- The main factor of production in forestry is renewable natural forest resources. That is, land plots, water resources, various natural orchards and groves, timber, etc.;

- the presence of differences in natural and climatic conditions in the territory where forestry enterprises are located. After all, these factors directly affect the natural composition and productivity of forests;

- the cultivation of agricultural and timber products in forestry is carried out in conjunction with the activities of their ecosystem services. Because there is no possibility of transferring ecosystem services from one region to another. An example of this is the protective and biodiversity conservation functions of forests.

Figure 1. Features of agricultural production on forest fund lands

Based on the conducted research, the factors influencing the cultivation of agricultural products on forest fund lands can be divided into organizational, economic, social, and legal groups. At the same time, although the influence of technical, technological, and innovative factors is presented in scientific literature, their share in the conditions of our country is very small, therefore it was not taken into account.

The group of economic factors is directly related to the volume of production and efficiency. These factors include lease payments for forest fund lands, benefits, taxation (for legal entities), purchase prices, payment system, resource prices, export quotas, lending system, subsidy amounts and procedures, incentive instruments, payment terms and forms, population solvency, wage system, contractual relations, and others.

As organizational factors, it includes such factors as forms of economic management, the state of organization of leasing, the organization of training courses, conducting marketing research, providing information, an early warning system, promoting the efficient use of land and environmental protection, a monitoring system, drawing up penalties and the state of organization of inspection work.

The influence of legal factors, such as legal literacy, the procedure for leasing forest fund lands, regulations, the state of their implementation, the procedure for formalization, and the term of the contract, is becoming increasingly relevant year by year.

3. CONCLUSION.

Having studied the above-mentioned features and influencing factors, it can be said that the most important issue in the cultivation of agricultural products on forest fund lands is the lease of these lands. This issue is the first step and the main decisive lever of all relationships. Issues such as lease relations, payment rates, terms, operating procedures, forms of ownership, and the validity of contracts also arise at this level. Therefore, in the research, it is advisable to improve the procedure for leasing forest fund lands, differentiate the payment system, take into account the specifics of the regions and the products grown, and also harmonize it with the forestry development strategy.

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